

Evaluation of Phytochemical and Antifungal Activities in Leaves and Fruit Extract of *Terminalia Chebula*

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are those that are commonly used in treating and preventing specific ailments and diseases, and that is generally considered to play a beneficial role in health care. The recent realization about the need for conservation has forced the concerned agencies to take up some steps in this regard but there are numerous constraints. Different studies show that *T. chebula* is routinely used as a traditional medicine to cure several ailments such as fever, cough, diarrhea, gastroenteritis, skin diseases, candidacies, urinary tract infection, and wound infections. That's why a study was planned to investigate the antifungal activity and phytochemical compounds in *T. chebula*. The fruits and leaves extracts of *T. chebula* were used for antifungal activity and phytochemical analysis. Antifungal activity of methanol, ethanol, and acetone extracts was evaluated against *A. flavors* and *F. oxysporum* by the poison food technique by using Sobourands agar medium. The methanolic, ethanolic, and acetone extracts of *T. chebula* leaves and fruit produced a significant zone of inhibition against two tested fungi in the range of 13 to 52.5 mm/Ml. For qualitative analysis of *T. chebula* of hot water extract and solvent extraction by soxhlet extraction method was used. The result revealed the presence of medically active compounds in plants that are carbohydrates, protein, phenols, tannins, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides. Our results show that *T.chebula* is an important medicinal plant having antifungal compounds and this species is recommended for further studies.

Keywords: Antifungal, Plants, Phenols, Leaves, Fruit

INTRODUCTION

Restorative plants are those plants that are normally utilized in treating and forestalling explicit infirmities and infections, and that is by and large considered to assume a useful part in medical care (Srivastava et al., 1996). Restorative plants (MP) are significant for the occupationns of helpless networks from one side of the planet to the other. The majority of medicated plants are belongs to blooming plants Out of the 32000 different types of higher plants (Prance, 2001).

There are about 10% are consumed therapeutically. Assessments suggested that all over the world the plant which is used in medicine has business near about \$ 5 trillion (US) by 2050 (Sarasa et al., 2012). It is observed that people, as well as different creatures, are utilizing restorative plants (Imtiaz et al., 2023) and animals (Umair et al., 2022; Muhammad et al., 2023) to self-medicate in a cycle mentioned as ethnobiology (Saeed et al., 2022). Such ethnobotanical information was gained by examining creature conduct, especially regarding wiped out creatures, and by meeting native networks. Pakistan, given its special topography along with the Himalayas, Hindu-kush, and Karakorum which the height starts from 0 to 8611 m and in this way has an assortment of climatic zones and rich flower variety (Altaf and Umair, 2022). Pakistan has round about 6,000 types of long plants (Ali and Qaiser, 1986).

Important thing is that 12% of the greenery is consumed therapeutically and very few plants are sent out. There is a gigantic unrefined medication market framework that is subject to wild plant species. Both human and creature infirmities are treated using restorative spices. Certain plant species are viewed as explicit for a specific ailment in majority cases, but once in a while, they have blended-use. In Pakistan approximately, these are 130,000 homeopaths, 455 Vadis, and 39,584 hakims enlisted where about 457 Tibbi medical shops and centers provide the drug to the population. Among that 95 dispensaries developed under common divisions of nearby bodies and Rustic Turn of events. There are 300-350 House fabricate organizations and around 300 organizations forming medications. Pakistan has considered one of the main countries that produced restorative plants (Ali and Qaiser, 1986).

It's undeniably true that 25% of all clinical solutions are huge depending on products getting from plants (Sarasa et al., 2012) Currently perceived worldwide as a medical care asset. The World Wellbeing Association (WHO) has brought up that conventional medication is a significant patron toward wellbeing objectives. As per the WHO, as numerous as 80% of human beings in the world rely upon customary medication for their important medical care needs. There are impressive financial advantages in the advancement of native medications and the utilization of restorative plants for the treatment of different infections. Anything that might be the circumstance, the biodiversity is being influenced and the number of inhabitant's invaluable plants is currently waning quickly. (Khanet al 2015).Quantities of phytochemical constituents have been discovered to be related to the medication like tannins, chebulinic corrosive, ellagic corrosive, Gallic corrosive, punicalagin, and flavonoids. Plants has been all around answered to have anti-diabetic, anti-bacterial (Nazer et al., 2023), anti-fungal (Kumar et al., 2023), anti-virul (Adil, 2021), cancer prevention agent (Hassan and Bhat, 2022; Umair et al., 2022), antiviral, anti-mutagenic, anti-cancerous, anti-ulcer, and wound mending exercises. Moreover, *T. chebula* has been utilized broadly in the readiness of numerous Ayurvedic plans for irresistible sicknesses like ongoing ulcers, leucorrhoea, pyorrhoea, and parasitic diseases of the skin.

T. chebula is being regularly consumed as conventional medicine by famous tribal of Tamil Nadu to fix a few illnesses like fever, hack, the runs, skin sicknesses, gastroenteritis, candidacies, urinary plot contamination, and wound diseases (Rao and Nammi, 2006). Plant natural products seem to have advanced complex anti-toxin mixtures to fix different infections like disease, cardiovascular, stomach related, and pathogenic microscopic organisms. A fluid concentrate of *T. chebula* shows antifungal action against various yeasts. It is successful against the dermatophyte, Epidermophyton and pathogenic yeast *Candida albicans*. Its inhibitory impact on three dermatophytes (*Trichophyton spp.*) and 03 yeasts (*Candida spp.*) has been reported. (Chattopadhyay and Bhattacharyya, 2007). That's why a study was planned to investigate the antifungal activity and Phytochemical compounds in *T. chebula* using leaves and fruits of the plant. Main objectives of the study were to evaluation of phytochemical and antifungal activities in leaves and fruit extract of *Terminalia chebula*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

PLANT MATERIAL COLLECTION

The Leaves and fruit of *T. chebula* were collected from the nursery of Lahore (Patoki). The collected material was identified by the plant expert from the department of forestry in the Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The voucher specimen was deposited in the laboratory of forestry, the Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

CHEMICALS CONSTITUENTS:

Methanol, 200ml distilled water, ethanol, acetone, 0.2% solution of Ninhydrin, 2ml of iodine,

2% solution of FeCl₃, Magnesium ribbon, conc.HCL chloroform,conc.H₂SO₄

PREPARATION OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *T. CHEBULA* ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF *T. CHEBULA*

First of all, the sample of bark and fruit were washed thoroughly with tap water. The samples were dried in the oven for 24 hours at 70°C. After this, the sample was ground in a high-capacity grinding machine. The coarse sample was sieved in different sizes of sieves.

The samples were weighed on the weight machine. A total of 250 gm powder of bark and fruit was put in a glass beaker and then added 500 ml of methanol gradually and mixed with a stirrer of about 5 to 10 minutes. The prepared solution was covered with aluminum foil for one week. After one week, the samples were filtered through Whitman no. 1 filter paper and the resulting filtrate was air-dried through pores of aluminum foil.

After one month, all remaining methanol was evaporated and the extract was obtained in the form of crystals. Now the samples are ready for different tests.

MICRO-ORGANISMS

Two main tests are *A. flavus* and *F. oxysporum* in which filamentous fungi were gained. Test strain was maintained by Sabourauds Agar at the temperature of 28°C. The Potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium was prepared in flasks and purified. The given pour into plates inserts into fungal cultures. Then hatched at about temp of 25 °C for one week.

POISON FOOD METHOD

The process of antifungal of abstracts was assessed against the two the named *A. flavous* and *F. oxysporum* by using the poisoned food method. The whole medium was then dispensed into plates. For PDA medium, samples having 1 ml of fruit and also leaves abstracts were added. The samples were carefully mixed by using stirring. The mycelia discs which is taken from the culture of the fungi test which was grown on the PDA medium petri plate for one week were used for immunization in the middle of Petri plate. Appropriate control was kept in which the cultured disc was grown under similar conditions on PDA medium without any abstracts. The given plates were immunized at temp 25°C. The %age inhibition which is given in the Table was obtained by using the following formula (Pinto et al., 1998):

$$\text{Inhibition\%} = \frac{dc-dt}{dc} * 100$$

In which dc is used as mycelial growth in control and dt is used as mycelial growth in treatments.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *T.CHEBULA*

PREPARATION OF PLANT EXTRACTS

HOT WATER EXTRACT

By taking 5mg of totally dried powdered-shaped plant fruit and putting it in the glass beaker. The water of quantity about 200 ml was added to the given powder. This prepared mixture was put on a hot plate for heating persistence with non-stop thrilling at temp ranging between 30-40°C for about 3 hours. Then the given water abstract was filtered by using filter paper and that filtrate was utilized for the Phyto-chemical test. The water extract was not in us then they kept in refrigerator.

SOLVENT EXTRACTION

Prepared Crude abstract was prepared by Soxhlet abstraction technique. By using this technique took 20mg of fruit powdered and equally filled in the thimble and mined it with a

different solvent having 250ml individually. The Solvents which are used were acetone methanol and ethanol. The procedure of abstraction carries on for 24 hours till the solvent becomes colorless which is present in the siphon tube of an extractor. Then the abstract was put into a beaker and used hot plate and heating at a range between 30- 40 °C till all the solvent evaporated completely. The dried abstract was put in a freezer for future work in Phyto-chemical tests.

QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

TEST FOR CARBOHYDRATES

IODINE TEST

In this test the Crude extract and Iodine having 2ml mixed with each other. The color changed to dark blue/purple which indicate the existence of carbohydrates.

TEST FOR PROTEINS

NINHYDRIN TEST

Crude fruit abstracts boiled with solution of Ninhydrin having 2ml of 0.2%, the violet color showed which changed to on heating that proved the presence of protein.

TEST FOR STEROID

The Crude abstract of fruit was mixed with chloroform having 2ml of pure H₂SO₄ was put from another side. At bottom of the chloroform the red color appeared which showed the presence of steroids. One more test was performed by using 2ml of chloroform mixing with prepared crude extract after that 2ml of conc. acetic acid and H₂SO₄ were put into the abstracts. The formation of a greenish color showed the existence of steroids.

TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS

SHINODA TEST

0.5% of each portion was dissolved in ethanol, warmed and then filtered. Three pieces of Mg chips was added to the filtrate followed by few drops of conc. HCl. A pink orange or red to purple coloration indicated the presence of flavonoids.

TEST FOR GLYCOSIDES

SALKOWSKI'S TEST

Chloroform with 2ml mixed up with Crude extract. After that added 2ml of conc. H₂SO₄ was put sensibly and then shaken slightly. After some time reddish brown color which indicated the existence of steroidal ring.

TEST FOR PHENOLS

The Crude fruit abstract was added with the solution of 2ml of the 2% FeCl₃. The blue-green/black color indicated the existence of phenols.

TEST FOR TANNINS

Crude fruit abstract was added up with solution having 2ml of 2% FeCl₃. It showed the blue-green/black color which indicates the existence of phenols.

TEST FOR SAPONINS

The Crude abstract of fruit mixed up with distilled water having 5ml in a test tube and shaken energetically. The existence of stable foam was an indication of the existence of saponins.

RESULTS

The extract of fruit showed that protein, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, and steroids give a positive result and only carbohydrates show a negative result. The extract of leaves shows positive results in Proteins, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides, saponins, and carbohydrates showed negative results. The process of antifungal of leaves and fruit extract was assessed against the two names *A.flavous* and *F. oxysporum* by using poisoned food method.

The fruits and leaves extracts of *T.chebula* were evaluated for antifungal activity and phytochemical analysis. The obtained constituent possessed numerous medicinal, physiological, and pharmacological properties. The fruits and leaves contain many active secondary metabolites and use as curative agents and antiseptics the methanol extract analysis showed the presence of many Phytochemical constitute in all samples. *A. flavous* and *F. oxysporum* were assayed against all the test fungi as a positive control *T.chebula* be used for the antifungal test against *A. Flavous* and *F. oxysporum* causing disease in plants.

A. flavous and *F. oxysporum* were assayed against all the test fungi as a positive control. *T.chebula* has been found to be used for the antifungal test against *A. flavous* and *F. oxysporum* causing diseases in plants. The extract of leaves of *T. chebula* was used. Antifungal activity on leaves extract of *T. chebula* against *A. flavous* by poison food method using sabouraud agar (potatoDextrose Agar PDA) medium at 25c for one week. The whole medium was dispensed into plates. Appropriate control was kept in which the cultured disc was grown under the similar conditions on PDA medium without any abstracts.

Table 1: Antifungal activities of leaves extract of *T. chebula*

Test organism	Co	EtOH	MeOH	Ace
<i>A.flavous</i>	23.5±0.01	23±0.1	23.25±0.5	23.25±0.2
<i>F.oxysporum</i>	43.25±0.02	25.75±0.1	26±0.5	26±0.2

Control=Co, ethanolic extract =EtOH, methanolic extract = MeOH ,acetone=Ace; Mean diameter of growth (mm)±SD

A. flavous and *F.oxysporum* were assayed against all the test fungi as a positive control. *T. chebula* have been found to be used for the antifungal test against *A. flavous* and *F. oxysporum* causing diseases in plants. The extract of fruit of *T. chebula* was used.

Table 2: Antifungal activities of fruit extract of *T. chebula*.

Testorganism	Co	EtOH	MeOH	Ace
<i>A.flavous</i>	33.15±0.01	21.5±0.1	21.5±0.5	21.5±0.2

<i>F.oxysporum</i>	52.5±0.02	13±0.1	13.5±0.5	13.5±0.2
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Mean diameter of growth(mm)±SD, control=Co, ethanolic extract = EtOH, methanolic extract = MtOH ,acetone=Ace;

ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF ETHANOL, METHANOL AND ACETONE EXTRACT OF LEAVES OF *T.CHEBULA* AGAINST FUNGAL STRAIN *A. FLAVOUS*

Antifungal activity on fruit extracts of *T.chebula* against *A.flavous* by poison food method using sabouraud agar (potato Dextrose Agar PDA) medium at 25c for one week. The whole medium was dispensed into plates. Appropriate control was kept in which the cultured disc was grown under similar conditions on PDA medium without any abstracts.

Antifungal activity of ethanol, methanol and acetone extract of leaves of *T.chebula* against fungal strain *F.oxysporum*. Antifungal activity on fruit extract of *T.chebula* against *F.oxysporum*. The whole medium was dispensed into plates. Appropriate control was kept in which the cultured disc was grown under the similar conditions on PDA medium without any abstracts.

ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF ETHANOL, METHANOL AND ACETONE EXTRACT OF FRUIT OF *T.CHEBULA*

AGAINST FUNGAL STRAIN *F. OXYSPORUM*

Antifungal activity on fruit extract of *T.chebula* against *F.oxysporum* poison food method using sabouraud agar (potato Dextrose Agar PDA) medium at 25c for one week. The whole medium was dispensed into plates. Appropriate control was kept in which the cultured disc was grown under the similar conditions on PDA medium without any abstracts.

The *T.chebula* consist of a few organic compositions which are given certain phybiological action on the body of human being and those bioactive elements which include carbohydrates, alkaloids, phenols , tannins, steroids , and flavonoids. These products are utilized by the primary or some secondary level metabolism of living creatures. The secondary metabolisms are taxonomical and chemical points of view of very changed mixtures with ambiguous functions. They are used in human scientific research, cure process, agriculture, and veterinary. A very high number of phytochemicals that belongs to many chemical types are shown to have inhibitory possessions to all kinds of virus. (cowan and M.M 1999).

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT FRACTION FRUIT EXTRACT

In present study results, phytochemical analysis of fruit of *T. chebula* shows that proteins, phenols, Tannins, Flavanoids, Saponins, Steroids and Glycosides content was present in methanol extract. The carbohydrates were absent in in methanol extract as indicated in table

Table 3: Phytochemical analysis of fruit extract of *T. chebula*

S.NO	Phytochemical	F. Methanol
1	Protein	+ve
2	Phenols	+ve
3	Tannins	+ve
4	Flavanoids	+ve
5	Saponins	+ve
6	Steroids	+ve
7	Carbohydrates	-ve

8	Glycosides	+ve
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PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF LEAVES EXTRACT

The present study results revealed that in phytochemical analysis of leaves of *T.chebula* Phenols, Tannins, Flavanoids, Steroids, Glycosides were present in methanol extract. Our results also shows that proteins, Saponins and Carbohydrates were absent in methanol extract as indicated in table (Table 4).

Table 4: Phytochemical analysis of leaves of *T. chebula*.

Sr. NO	Phytochemical	L. Methanol
1	Protein	-ve
2	Phenols	+ve
3	Tannins	+ve
4	Flavanoids	+ve
5	Saponins	-ve
6	Steroids	+ve
7	Carbohydrates	-ve
8	Glycosides	+ve

DISCUSSION

All the traditional system of medicines in India such as ayurved, sidha, unani has documented several plants to be of high therapeutic value thus giving them medicinal importance. The use of the herbal medicines has increased due to number of benefits. Herbal medicine's recognition is gradually increasing in the world as they are safe and all natural. *Terminalia chebula* consists of number of phytochemical constituents which are found to be associated with the plant extract that include mainly chebulic acid, gallic acid, ellagic acid, tannins acid, amino acid, flavanoids, like luteolin, rutins and quercetin etc. All these compounds are found to be responsible for many of pharmacological activities. *T.chebula* is an important herbal drug as it is used for treating many diseases including diseases such as cancer. Many pharmacological investigations have been carried out based on its chemical constituents. This review shows some pharmacological and pharmacognistical studies on haritaki. I hope that this article provides an insight to the studies, and hope this review provides a generalization that will help the students who search for the information on *T.chebula* which is considered the most important medicinal herb in all system of medicines. Based on the presence of secondary metabolites, the medicinal plants were used to treat human ailments.

The assessment of phytochemical and antifungal activity in *Terminalia chebula* leaves and fruit extract provides vital insights into the therapeutic potential of this medicinal plant (Das et al., 2020). Phytochemical research reveals the presence of bioactive chemicals known for their various pharmacological characteristics, such as tannins, flavonoids, and alkaloids (Kaushik et al., 2021). The extracts' antifungal properties highlight their potential as natural options for treating fungal infections. *Terminalia chebula*, often known as Haritaki, has long been valued for its antibacterial properties in traditional medicine (Gupta, 2012). This research advances our understanding of the plant's bioactive elements and their prospective

applications in the pharmaceutical and healthcare industries, opening the way for future natural medicine research and development.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The *T. chebula* is commonly found in India and in some adjacent areas such as Pakistan, also in the South-West of China. Several phytochemical compositions are found to be linked with medicine such as punicalagin, ellagic acid, chebulinic acid, gallic acid, and tannins. Additionally, *T. chebula* is declared to have wound curing, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, antiviral, anti-cancerous, antibacterial, antiulcer, anti-mutagenic, and antifungal activities. As the aqueous solutions of *T. chebula* display antifungal progress against various yeasts. Their inhibitory consequences on various these yeasts as well as dermatophytes antifungal progress for steroids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, alkaloids, terpenoids, and flavonoids In different plants, flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and various fragrant mixtures of metabolites are highly difficult to cover contrivance against entering different microorganisms and various slayers like insects and herbivores. There are two different tested filamentous fungi, *A. flavors* and *F. oxysporum*, which are obtained. The experienced stresses were sustained on Sabouraud's Agar at a temperature around about 28°C. The Potato dextrose agar moderate were organized in the bottles and purified. The Pours into testing plates after freezing enclosure fungal culture. Hatched at a temperature of about 25 °C for one week. by using the poisoned food method, the Antifungal process of all abstracts was marked against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus flavors*. *T. chebula* possesses a few organic products that are used to deliver the final functional process to a human being. These bioactive elements include flavonoids, tannins, carbohydrates, phenols, carbohydrates, sapiens, and alkaloids. These products are produced by using the primary or secondary processes or metabolisms of various living organisms. Secondary metabolites consist of taxonomically and chemically particularly different compositions with ambiguous functions that are commonly used in human being treatment, scientific research, the fields of agriculture, veterinary medicine, and other countless areas. Many phytochemicals, which belong to many chemical programs, are displayed for having inhibitory effects on different microorganisms.

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